

Virtual biome: Exploring The Definition of Life, Self-Organization, and Artificial Intervention

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ABSTRACT

In "Virtual Biome: Exploring The Definition of Life, Self-Organization, and Artificial Intervention," the author embarks on an innovative exploration of the blurred lines between organic life and artificial constructs. Through the development of virtual amoebas using Object-Oriented Programming, p5.js, and HTML, this essay delves into how these digital entities, with their capacity for individual responses and self-organization, challenge traditional notions of life. By integrating dynamic Perlin noise, random movements, and interactive elements that mimic natural processes such as feeding and communication, the project stretches the definition of "creature," inviting readers to reconsider the superiority of natural over artificial life. Drawing on post-humanist thought and the philosophy of decentering humanity, the essay examines the boundaries between the organic and inorganic, the emergence of self-organization in virtual entities, and the implications of human intervention in creating artificial life forms. It reflects on the philosophical and theoretical underpinnings that informed the creation of these virtual amoebas, offering a critical analysis of the intersection between natural science, technology, and art. The work engages with seminal texts and theories in cybernetics, political ecology, and actor-network theory, providing a comprehensive exploration of the potentialities and challenges inherent in the digital simulation of life.

1. INTRODUCTION

This essay serves as an introduction and further elucidation of my interactive game based on web pages. The project could be accessed through the following link:

<https://huichuan1999.github.io/Theory-VirtualCreatures/>

with the text-less, mobile version:

<https://huichuan1999.github.io/Amoebas-HTML/>

Video of audience playing:

<https://vimeo.com/822992079>

Using Object-Oriented Programming (OOP), p5.js, and HTML languages, I created virtual amoebas with individual differences and responses to external stimuli. The addition of dynamic Perlin noise, random crawling trajectories and sound input imbues these simple shapes with lifelike qualities, stretching the definition of "creature" and exploring the boundaries between life and artificial constructs. As if experiencing a biological stress response, they tend to communicate with each other by changing color and connect by a line when in proximity, like exchanging pheromones. If user clicking on the screen, yellow dots generate as food, the amoebas would move towards them, consuming them, and get bigger. The interface provides buttons to let human clear food, add creatures, kill them, or restart the life game. Codes looming on the screen reveal the inner nature of these virtual creatures.

Witnessing these virtual amoebas, which possess primitive structures and simple logic of activity, yet can develop intricate and splendid forms and efficiently transmitting "nutrients" or "pheromones," challenges human arrogance in assuming superiority and invites us to reconsider the definition of life. Drawing inspiration from post-humanist and "decentering humanity" approaches, this article seeks to demonstrate the creative endeavor, concomitantly the theoretical background and philosophical inspiration behind my project's materialization. In a more tangible sense, these essay will primarily focus on the examination of boundaries between organic and inorganic entities, the emergence of self-organization, and the potential implications of human involvement in the creation of artificial life forms. Finally, the essay also tries to demonstrate the rationale of my practical process.

Figure 1. A screenshot of my project.

2. NATURAL SCIENCE AND SELF-ORGANIZING OF LIFE

My longstanding interest in natural science led me to research the morphology and structure of ancient organisms, particularly the earliest Ediacaran biota, whose main functions were very primitive, basically absorbing nutrients and excreting waste. Because in the absence of significant predators, hard shells, vision, and athleticism were unnecessary, resulting in many creatures expanding voraciously in a fractal manner. During their morphological evolution, cells in these organisms continuously replicated themselves according to specific rules. Fractals serve as an early and primitive example of self-organization, which contributed to the unique morphology of the Ediacaran biota. Regarding the essence of these rules, L-system may give us a clear answer. L-systems can model or classify the fractal structures of these ancient life forms, which could be a potentially good future research direction. At the same time, employing L-systems to simulate the aesthetic forms of plants shares a similar underlying principle. In L-system, fractals, plants, fractals can be viewed as a manifestation of self-organization among cells, where countless tiny individuals come together to grow in the direction specified by fixed formulas, like leading by the "turtle"(Szilard and Quinton, 1979, pp. 8–13) to rewrite the path, to form a new, larger entity, which can often be summarized by the formulas in one or several recursive functions. This represents a step forward from primitive to more advanced life forms, echoing the evolutionary progression observed in nature. (Prusinkiewicz and Hanan, 1988)

Figure 2 - Figure 4

In Utomata coded by Lior Gen Gai, the dynamic behavior of systems simulating the growth, expansion, and evolution of biological communities can be described through simple rules and local interactions.

Figure 5. Utomata.

In Daniel Shiffman's Genetic Algorithms, referencing Darwin's natural selection, the evolution of code-based organisms is divided into three steps: 1) Creating a population, 2) Selection, and 3) Reproduction. In this practice, Arrays and classes replace the creation of populations, computer-generated random numbers replace the process of natural selection, and crossover and mutation functions replace reproduction. By iterating through these three steps over multiple generations, the algorithm simulates the process of evolution, enabling the population to adapt and optimize its performance in response to the given task or environment. The process continues until a predefined termination condition is met, such as reaching a certain number of generations or achieving a specific level of fitness in the population. (Shiffman, 2009)

In these studies, we can see how biological systems generate complexity and adaptability through self-organization and self-regulation. These processes play a significant role in driving the evolution of primitive life forms and in defining life itself.

3. EXPLORING THE BOUNDARIES: DEFINING LIFE IN THE INTERSECTION OF HUMANS AND MACHINES

Exploring computer technology revealed a subtle connection between technology and life, The Ediacaran biota, fractals and L-systems, Utomata, Genetic Algorithm, and various computational methods provide valuable insights into the morphology and behavior of these virtual organisms, raising intriguing questions about the nature of life and the potential for consciousness in artificially created entities. These leads me to investigate philosophical implications such as artificial life and the definition of life. This includes Descartes' mechanistic philosophy, which posits that all life forms, except humans, are intricate machines resembling clockwork gears, and the dualistic oppositions between mind-matter, organic-inorganic, and natural-mechanical.

In this point, I noticed that metaphorical transformations in describing machines and biology challenge our understanding of life, as certain metaphors, technical devices imitate human body functions, then organisms are described in technological terms, as Schrödinger introduced into scientific discourse the central metaphor of molecular biology: the chromosome as a message written in code(Nikolai Krementsov, 1996), following which new machines appear based on the mechanism of the functioning of these technology perceived bodies and so on(Slava Gerovitch, 2002), which leads me to believe that the "definition" of life may just be a game of metaphorical transformations. For example, the most famous human-computer metaphor is Turing's "can machine think?" (1950)

In John Von Neumann's "The Computer and the Brain," he drew comparisons between the brain and computer memory, thinking and information processing, cognition and programming, as well as learning and self-organization. He believed that the performance of many aspects could be evaluated using the same parameters, such as processing speed. (John Von Neumann, Churchland and Patricia Smith Churchland, 2000)These insights laid the foundation for later research in cognitive science, computational neuroscience, and computational psychology. Similarly, In Norbert Wiener's cybernetics, there are also these corresponding relationships, such as: server mechanisms with computers, body with feedback-operated server mechanisms, life with entropy-reducing processes, humans with information sources, human communication with transmission of encoded messages, human brain with networks of logical elements, and the human mind with digital computers (Wiener, 2013)

What exactly sets us apart from machines? Our neurons resemble networks of logical elements, our memory is like storage chips, our thinking is akin to information processing, our cognition parallels programming, and our learning emulates like the self-organizing ability of algorithms... What is life, after all? Is it an entropy-reducing process? And what about the body? Does it function like a feedback-operated server mechanism? Then, what constitutes our consciousness and personality?

Concerning these, multiple scholars have coined a constellation of neologism. Driesch believes it is entelechy(1908), and Bennet Jane calls it vital force: It exists inside the biological organism that is irreducible to matter because it is a free and undetermined agency. Like the vitalists who preceded them, defenders of the culture of life believe there to be something profoundly inadequate about a mechanistic metaphysic(2009). While new concepts are formed, established are also being challenged. Nicholas Burns believed that Pavlov degraded the organism and reduced it to a reactive automaton, replacing it with Turing's metaphor of the human brain and computer(2009).In "What Technology Wants," Kevin Kelly views technology as a life-like form called the "Technium." (2011)

These analogies have completely blurred the line between humans and machines, ultimately giving birth to the concept of cyborgs. A cyborg is a cybernetic organism, a hybrid of machine and organism, a creature of social reality as well as a creature of fiction. Donna Haraway sees the cyborg as a cybernetic organism, a hybrid of machine and organism, a creature of social reality, and a virtual creature(2018). Reflecting on human beings, we are actually not much different from machines. Carolyn Merchant admitted that the organic and mechanical philosophies of nature cannot be viewed as strict dichotomy(2008). What on the surface often appeared as a struggle between organic and mechanistic views of the world, may in the end prove to be a battle between old and new machine metaphors.(Slava Gerovitch, 2002)

Next, I want to use my project to reflect on the implications of blurring the line between human and machine, as well as the ethical considerations in creating and intervening in artificial life.

4. ABOUT MY PRACTICES: PHOTOMICROGRAPHY AESTHETICS AND PHILOSOPHY

In my early experiments, when I added dynamic PerlinNoise to a simple circle, it started to behave like some of the most common amoebas, randomly stretching out their appendages to swim and crawl. (figure 6). And when I add the sound input and apply it as the maximum value of the noise, it seems to have some rudimentary intelligence, it will respond To the excessive sound, be disturbed, and quickly extend the sharp tentacles, like being irritated or hurt(figure 8).

Figure 6-8. screenshots of my code practice.

Then, I delved into Object-Oriented-programming (OOP), made a creature class, and arrays to contain a bunch of them. I incorporated a significant amount of randomness and noise to create individual variations among the virtual creatures, while using trigonometric functions like $\sin()$ and $\cos()$ to simulate a meandering crawl.

Figure 9. Screenshot of my web game playing on mobile phone.

These random numbers seem to embody the entelechy of these virtual beings, with me acting as a "God" orchestrating their existence in the laboratory. I even designed a series of buttons to grant users the power to remove foods, create and destroy them. Additionally, I employed a state machine in the process. Users provide food for the creatures by clicking the mouse. When the creatures are close to the food, they alter their trajectory and accelerate towards it, though there is a chance they may miss the target. As their cores overlap with the food, they are considered to be consuming it, causing their radius to expand until it surpasses the "full threshold" limit. Once this limit is exceeded, the creatures enter a full state. After leaving the food source, their radius gradually contracts to its original size, and the cycle repeats. Considering the perspectives mentioned earlier, when the virtual creatures I create form a group and begin to exhibit collective behavior and engage in communication, they seem to possess genuine intelligence.

As a visual artist, inspired by microbiological photography, I strive to make these creature movements and trajectories appear natural and vivid in color and compositional aesthetics. Life is an aesthetic organism, and the organism is a new active image of self-setting, a mere aesthetically controlled organism, that searched for and selectively accepted environmental events. (Slava Gerovitch,2002)

Here, using HTML and CSS languages, I present the JavaScript code that constructs these creatures, as that is their true essence, along with the metaphors and questions on the page. If you click some of them, some new window will pop up, showing some random fractal shapes and some of the prints I made, encased in glass slides. These random fractals are also generated by me using JavaScript, which indicates the possibility of future direction of evolution of these single-celled organisms. By observing the printing amoeba in the glass slide, some ink dots left by the printer can be found, indicating that even artificially created things have the same regular details as real creatures at the microscopic level.

Figure 10. Screenshot of the popup windows in my web mini game.

As people move the mouse, they only materialize when you hold the mouse, and the glyphs appear in a red hue—reminiscent of the color of blood seen during dissection. But do virtual creatures have "blood"? Further reflection on the nature of life, observation, and perfection in the digital world could be prompt:

Who is observing? Does it still matter if the observer is not human?

What is "perfection"? Is digital perfection truly perfect? (e.g., we always use perfect geometry to simulate everything in the real world in 3D software)

What kind of organisms are these virtual creatures? Do they fit the definition of life?

Could everything in the digital world represent a new form of life?

Figure 11. Screenshot of the texts in my web game.

As you can observe, I have deliberately incorporated a variety of visual metaphors in this project. The light blue background grid evokes a sense of rationality, reminiscent of a laboratory setting. Here, concepts of order and chaos, as well as the inorganic and organic, are juxtaposed. This contrast encourages viewers to contemplate whether the developmental processes of organisms are not simply "the result of a special constellation of factors known already to the sciences of the inorganic," (Bennett, 2010) but rather stem from an "autonomy peculiar" to life itself. However, for Driesch, the laboratory and the inquisitive scientist represented the optimal access points to uncover the principles of life(1908). Thus, it was always crucial "to reflect once more with an open mind on the actual biological data" (Bennett, 2010).

Figure 12. Screenshot of the overview of my web game.

5. REFLECTION AND CONCLUSION

As we reach the end of this article, several new thought-provoking questions emerge: Does the created amoeba cluster possess any form of subjective consciousness? Are these virtual life forms merely "illusions" generated by computer algorithms and random numbers?

From the perspective of "things," these virtual creatures may appear passive, merely accepting their programmed interactions and states. However, as these interactions and states grow increasingly complex, how do we define the concepts of "life" and "death"? And as we write programs to create these virtual entities, does the "mind" live in our own brain follow a similar set of processes?

In conclusion, These questions serve as a reminder that our understanding of life, consciousness, and the boundaries between the organic and inorganic world continues to evolve. I will, as always, keep an open mind and continue to explore in the field of biology and life.

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Image Reference:

Image source:

Figure 2: Available at:

<http://www.ediacaran.org/charnia-masoni.html> (Accessed: 1st May, 2023)

Figure 3: Available at:

https://geologicnow.punctumbooks.com/4_McKay.php

Figure4: A screenshot of Przemyslaw Prusinkiewicz and Hanan, J. (2013). *Lindenmayer Systems, Fractals, and Plants*. Springer Science & Business Media. P.25.

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